

INCREASING THE LIFETIME OF CONVEYOR BELTS

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Abstract: This article presents the methods of connecting conveyor belts used in mining enterprises, and developed new methods for connecting conveyor belts. Preliminary results of experimental studies on the developed new methods are also presented.

Keywords: conveyor belt, connection methods, rollers, rubber-fabric belt, rubber-cable belts, cold method.

The extraction of minerals and their delivery to the consumer's destination or processing plant is the mainstay of any country's economic growth industry. One of the most effective ways is to transport rock mass through conveyors in mines with a depth of 400-700 meters.

Today's experience shows that one of the biggest problems with belt conveyors is that the belts often break and require repairs. We know that conveyor belt maintenance process takes a certain amount of time, as a result of which continuous transportation will stop and its productivity will decrease. In order to avoid such situations, it is necessary to improve the methods of connecting the conveyor belt.

The belt is the most expensive element of the conveyor. The cost of belt repair and replacement is a major part of the cost of operating a belt conveyor.

Today, the most advanced and efficient way to cut conveyor belts and cut the belt in the form of a ladder (Fig. 1) is the most advanced and effective.

Figure 1. The method of cutting the conveyor belt in the form of a ladder

1 – upper cover, 2 – fabric cover, 3 – lower cover.

There are several disadvantages of connecting conveyor belts in this way, which include:

- absence of frictional forces on the cut inner surface of the strips;
- high sliding force compared to the frictional force in the lining and lining parts of the strips
- frequent disconnection of the conveyor belts from the connection point has a negative effect on its productivity and increases the cost of repairs.

Increasing the durability of conveyor belts requires the introduction of new innovative and high-performance technical solutions.

Therefore, it will be necessary to develop a new method of connecting conveyor belts. In this case, it may be more effective and economical to cut the facing of the tapes and connect them to each other by shortening the distances between them by cutting the facing part of the tapes in the ladder method, which is currently used. The special features of the belt lining, its smallness, i.e., the closeness of the interval distance and the presence of rows connecting to each other, increase the productivity of continuous transport by increasing the productivity of the conveyor belt by extending its service life. Figure 2(a,b) shows a cross-sectional view of a conveyor belt.

2 – picture. Conveyor belt connected by cross-sectional surface.

a – view of the left part of the belt; b – view of the right part of the belt

Carrying out experimental tests on checking the connection of conveyor belts on the cross-sectional surface allowed to establish the relationship between F - the pulling force and N - the reaction force directed along the normal vector of the belt.

Connecting the conveyor belts on this cross-sectional surface first of all increased its mechanical strength, extended the service life, increased the gravity reactions of the internal surfaces of the belts, and led to high reliability.

By cutting the conveyor belt on the cross-sectional surface, it increases the resistance of the belts to mechanical forces, while reducing the cost of repairing the conveyor belts, as a result, it is possible to reduce the downtime for the repair of the belt by 7%.

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